

MSMEs Role In India

Gayanagarao M. M.

Asst. Prof. Vaidyanath College Parli.V

Corresponding Author – Gayanagarao M. M.

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.18501977

Abstract:

The MSMEs is considered as micro enterprise, Small enterprise and medium enterprises engaged in various economic activities such as manufacturing, processing and services. MSMEs classifications are based on their investment amount and annual turnover. MSMEs referred to as the backbone of nation's economic development. MSMEs contribute significantly to community development, infrastructure enhancement and improved living standards and is a key pillar of Government flagship "Make in India" Initiative and contributes nearly one-third to the India's GDP

Objectives of the Study:

1. To study the economic contribution of MSMEs sector
2. To study the Role of MSMEs
3. To study the Government Initiatives

Research methodology:

Descriptive methodology is adopted completely based on secondary data available from the press reports of the Ministry of Micro Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) on the websites.

Evolution of MSMEs Classification:

Pre 2006 Era: small scale Industries (SSI) were defined primarily based on investment limits with threshold for Small and Ancillary Industries.

MSMED Act 2006: Introduced the three-tire classification of Micro Small and Medium enterprises with investment limits for manufacturing and services enterprises.

Revised Classification (July 2020) the government of India removed the distinction between Manufacturing and Service sectors and introduced a composite criterion based on both investments and turn overs to classify MSMEs

Revised classification effective from Aril 1 2025:

The union budget 2025-26 introduced a series of measures aimed at strengthening the MSME sector by enhancing the credit access supporting first time entrepreneurs and promoting labour intensive industries.

- For Micro Enterprises up to Rupees 2.5 Crore for Investment limit and up-to Rupees 10 crore for turn over limit.
- For Small Enterprises up-to Rupees 25 Crore for Investment limit and up-to Rupees 100 Crore turn over limit.
- For Medium Enterprises up-to Rupees 125 Crore for Investment and up-to Rupees 500 Crore turn over limit

MSMEs Contribution to Economy:

- The share of MSMEs in the country's Gross Value Added (GAV) increasing from 27.3% in F.Y 2020-21 to 29.6% in F.Y 2021-22 and 30.1% in F.F. 2022-23 highlights its growing role in economic output.

- Exports from MSMEs have seen substantial growth rising from Rs.395 Lakh Crore in F.Y. 2020-21 to Rs.12.39 lakh Crore in F.Y. 2024-25. The number of exporting MSMEs has increasing from 52,849 in F.Y. 2020-21 TO 1,73,350 in F.Y. 2024-25(May 2024).
- MSMEs Contribution to India's export has steadily grown reaching to 43.59% in F.Y.2022-23 and 45.73% in F.Y.2023-24 and 45.79% in F.Y. 2024-25(MAY 2024)

Government Initiatives:

- Udaan Training Program for unemployment youth of J & K (SII & J&K)
- National Skill Certification and Monetary Rewards(STAR Scheme)
- Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana
- Apprenticeship Training
- Craftsmen Training (ITIs)
- Skill development in 34 Districts Affected by Left Wing extremism
- Up gradation of 1396 TTIs through PPP
- Capital goods scheme
- Excise duty concession to PWDs
- Custom Duty concession
- Financial Assistance for promotion of Youth Activities and Training (FAPYAT)
- National program for Youth Corps (NYC) Implemented through Nehru yuva Kendra Sangathan (NYKS)
- Development of Ayush Centers

The above list of schemes that Government of India implemented with an aim to encourage the Micro Small and Medium enterprises. These schemes are to promote financial support and procurement policies to capacity building and market integration. All these initiatives are to foster entrepreneurship and employment and integrating informal sector into formal sector.

Role of MSMEs:

1. Employment Generation: MSMEs provide employment opportunities particularly in Rural and semi urban areas. (September 2025) India's economy continues to expand rapidly with 6.82 Crore MSMEs registered on the Udyam Registration portal and Udyam Assist Platform (UAP) collectively employing 29.77 Crore people. Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu, and Uttar Pradesh dominate the MSME landscape accounting for 32% of all registrations Nationwide. Maharashtra leads with over 90 Lakh Registration (13%) followed by the Uttar Pradesh with 74Lakh (11%) and Tamil Nadu with 54.7Lakh (8%) these states have emerged as key Hubs for MSMEs activity.
2. E-Markets: Government E-Market place called GEM is the digital platform where the Government is actually focusing MSMEs. (March 2024) GEM has facilitated 5.8 Million Orders worth Rs.3, 87,006 crore serving 148,245 primary buyers and 215,743 secondary buyers. There is a increasing shift in digital payments.
3. Skill Development and Entrepreneurship Promotion: programs conducted under ESDP scheme benefitting 5, 66,410 individuals.

Conclusion:

MSMEs play a vital role in the Indian economy because it is a backbone substantially contributes towards employment generation, GDP, Exports, E-Markets, UPI's and empowering the India's youth in achieving the India's vision i.e. elevating India into a Dollar 5 Trillion economy by 2025. MSMEs contribute significantly to community development infrastructure enhancement and improved living standards.

References:

1. https://www.sidbi.in/uploads/Understanding_Indian_MSME_sector_Progress_and_Challenges_13_05_25_Final.pdf
2. <https://www.pib.gov.in/PressReleasePage.aspx?PRID=2099687®=3&lang=2>
3. <https://irjems.org/Volume-4-Issue-5/IRJEMS-V4I5P113.pdf>
4. https://msme.gov.in/sites/default/files/MSME_Schemes_English_0.pdf
5. <https://www.ibef.org/industry/msme>